

PRESTIGE AUTOMOBILE DISPLAY AND ITS IMPACT ON DINING EXPERIENCE AT KARRERA SHOWROOM CAFÉ IN ALABANG

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the impact of Prestige Automobile Displays on the dining experience at Karrera Showroom Café in Alabang, a unique venue combining high-end car showcases with a café environment. Utilizing the Servicescape Theory and Conspicuous Consumption Theory as frameworks, the researchers explored how automobile design, café environment, and visual appeal influence customer satisfaction, time spent, and perceived value for money. A descriptive-quantitative approach was employed, with data collected from 397 respondents through a structured survey. Findings revealed that luxury car displays significantly enhance the café's ambiance, creating a unique and memorable dining experience. Visual appeal emerged as the most influential factor, driving customer satisfaction and fostering positive word-of-mouth. Statistical analysis confirmed strong correlations between automobile display and dining satisfaction, time spent, and value perception, underscoring the strategic value of integrating prestige elements in hospitality settings. The study provided actionable insights for the hospitality and automotive industries, offering a model for blending luxury marketing with experiential dining to attract diverse customer demographics and promote brand prestige.

Keywords: *Prestige Automobile Display, Dining Experience, Customer Satisfaction*

INTRODUCTION

Creating a unique and captivating customer experience is essential for success in the competitive hospitality industry. This research investigates the impact of showcasing prestigious automobiles on the dining experience at the Karrera Showroom Café in Alabang. It seeks to explore the synergistic effect of combining automobile prestige with a dining environment that offers food and beverages, aiming to understand how high-end vehicles enhance customers' dining experience.

Under the Intellectual Property Code of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 8293), dealerships must ensure they have the proper authorization and licensing to sell branded luxury vehicles, protecting both the manufacturers' and consumers' rights. Article 1654 of the Civil Code of the Philippines (Republic Act No. 386) also mandates that the lessor maintain the leased items in optimal condition. † ensures that the prestigious vehicles displayed can be used for photographs, facilitating enjoyable interactions between the displays and customers, thereby enhancing the dining experience at the café.

The Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 9, "Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure," emphasizes fostering innovation and building sustainable infrastructure to

drive economic growth, social development, and environmental sustainability. Integrating prestigious automobiles with dining experiences in the hospitality industry exemplifies this goal by combining different sectors to create unique and innovative customer experiences. This approach enhances customer experience, promotes economic resilience, and supports climate action while ensuring equitable access and opportunities for all.

The researchers suggested a solution to the misconception that Karrera Showroom Café is only for vehicle buyers. They recommend improving communication through social media marketing and clear signage within the café to highlight that it welcomes all guests, regardless of their reason for visiting. Additionally, promoting the café's offerings and atmosphere during events can help attract a wider customer. Moreover, the study's results will add valuable insights to the limited research on this innovative marketing approach of combining a car showroom and café in the Philippine setting.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The primary goal of this research was to comprehensively examine the impact of Prestige Automobile Display on the Dining Experience of customers at Karrera Showroom Café Alabang.

Specifically, it aimed to address the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Occupation?
2. What is the level of Prestige Automobile Display in terms of?
 - 2.1 Automobile Design
 - 2.2 Café Environment
 - 2.3 Visual Appeal?
3. How does the Prestige Automobile Display affect the customers' Dining Experience in terms of?
 - 3.1 Dining Satisfaction
 - 3.2 Spent
 - 3.3 Value for Money?
4. Does the Prestige Automobile Display have any impact on the dining experience of customers at Karrera Showroom Café Alabang?

HYPOTHESIS

Ho: The Prestige Automobile Display does not have any impact on the dining experience at Karrera Showroom Café in Alabang

METHODOLOGY

This study used a descriptive design within a quantitative approach to systematically address the research problem. Data were collected through a survey and analyzed using statistical techniques. Rusyani et al. (2021) highlight that market studies commonly apply descriptive research to explore consumer buying patterns. The researcher employed simple random sampling to select respondents from the café customer population. This method ensured that each customer had an equal chance of being chosen, making it convenient since any diner could participate. A modified survey questionnaire served as the primary data collection instrument. This questionnaire was adapted from similar tools used in previous studies by Al-tit (2015), Ali et al. (2021), and Kaura et al. (2015), all of which are closely related to the current research. The questionnaire underwent a rigorous validation process involving experts, the adviser, and the Dean before receiving final approval from the RDE. Participants responded using a 4-point Likert Scale. Data collection occurred over nine days, from August 27 to September 4. The responses were entered into Excel and analyzed by a statistician using descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and standard deviation to interpret the study's key findings. The Spearman's Rho was used to measure the strength of the relationship between two variables with continuous or ordinal data that had a monotonic relationship. Mirtagioglu and Mendeş (2022) found Spearman's rho to be the most effective correlation method for monotonic relationships.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1

Summary of the Mean Scores and Standard Deviation of Prestige Automobile Display

Indicator	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Automobile Design	3.80	0.45	Strongly Agree
Café Environment	3.76	0.46	Strongly Agree
Visual Appeal	3.82	0.42	Strongly Agree
Composite Mean	3.79	0.44	Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.51-4.00 – Strongly Agree; 3.49 – Agree; 3.00 – Disagree; 1.00 – Strongly Disagree

.Table 1 summarizes the mean and standard deviation of prestige automobile display, with a composite mean of 3.79 and standard deviation of 0.44, interpreted as "Strongly Agree." It can be seen in the table that all indicators are "Strongly Agree." Visual Appeal has the highest mean for the indicators, with 3.82 for the mean and 0.44 for the standard deviation. The Café Environment got the lowest mean in all indicators, with a mean of 3.76 and a standard deviation of 0.46.

Table 2

Summary of the Mean Scores and Standard Deviation of Dining Experience

Indicator	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Dining Satisfaction	3.73	0.51	Strongly Agree
Time Spent	3.66	0.56	Strongly Agree
Value for money	3.61	0.58	Strongly Agree
Composite Mean	3.67	0.55	Strongly Agree

Legend: 3.51-4.00 – Strongly Agree; 3.49 – Agree; 3.00 – Disagree; 1.00 – Strongly Disagree

Table 2 summarizes the mean and standard deviation of dining experience, with a composite mean of 3.67 and a standard deviation of 0.55, interpreted as “Strongly Agree.” Dining satisfaction has the highest mean for the indicators, with 3.73 for the mean and 0.51 for the standard deviation. The value for money got the lowest mean in all indicators, with a mean of 3.61 and a standard deviation of 0.51.

Table 3

Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of Prestige Automobile Display and Dining Experience at Karrera Showroom Café

Level of Prestige Automobile Display	Dining Experience	Computed r - value	P - value	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
<i>Automobile Design</i>	<i>Dining Satisfaction</i>	0.385**	0.004	Reject	Significant
	<i>Time Spent</i>	0.383**	0.004	Reject	Significant
	<i>Value for Money</i>	0.248**	0.006	Reject	Significant
<i>Café Environment</i>	<i>Dining Satisfaction</i>	0.362**	0.004	Reject	Significant
	<i>Time Spent</i>	0.447**	0.003	Reject	Significant
	<i>Value for Money</i>	0.347**	0.004	Reject	Significant
<i>Visual Appeal</i>	<i>Dining Satisfaction</i>	0.336**	0.004	Reject	Significant
	<i>Time Spent</i>	0.340**	0.004	Reject	Significant
	<i>Value for Money</i>	0.315**	0.005	Reject	Significant

***Correlation is significant if the p-value is ≤ to 0.01 level of significance*

The study results indicate a statistically significant relationship between the level of prestige in automobile displays and customers' dining experience. Specifically, the design of the automobiles exhibited moderate positive correlations with dining satisfaction ($r = 0.385$, $p = 0.004$), time spent ($r = 0.383$, $p = 0.004$), and perceived value for money ($r = 0.248$, $p = 0.006$). These findings suggest that the presence of well-designed, luxurious cars contributes to a more fulfilling dining experience. Automobile design's visual and symbolic Appeal likely enhances emotional engagement, leading diners to perceive greater satisfaction and value. It aligns with Kim, Lee, and Jung's (2021) findings, which emphasized that luxury and aesthetic innovation elements in consumer environments significantly boost user satisfaction and engagement.

Similarly, the café environment—referring to how well the dining space integrates with the automobile display and its ambiance—showed positive correlations with dining satisfaction ($r = 0.362$, $p = 0.004$), time spent ($r = 0.447$, $p = 0.003$), and value for money ($r = 0.347$, $p = 0.004$). These results highlight the importance of atmosphere and immersive experience design in influencing customer behavior and perception. A well-curated space that combines hospitality with luxury elements like car displays may foster a sense of exclusivity and comfort, encouraging longer stays and greater satisfaction. Choe and Kim (2020) supported this by demonstrating that upscale restaurant environments significantly influence diners' emotional experiences and behavioral intentions. In addition, the visual Appeal of the automobile display itself was significantly correlated with satisfaction ($r = 0.336$, $p = 0.004$), time spent ($r = 0.340$, $p = 0.004$), and value for money ($r = 0.315$, $p = 0.005$). It further reinforces the role of aesthetic stimulation in enhancing the dining experience. Customers associate visually rich environments with higher perceived value, which may contribute to brand differentiation in a competitive food and beverage industry. Collectively, these findings support the view that prestige automobile displays act as powerful experiential tools that positively impact customer satisfaction, engagement, and perceived value when effectively integrated into dining settings.

CONCLUSION

The findings reveal that most of the respondents for the gender is male, comprising 215 respondents, or 54.16%. Regarding age, most respondents are 21 to 25, making up 137 respondents, or 34.51%. Students dominate the pool for occupation, with 183 respondents (46.10%). Regarding automobile design, the composite mean score across all statements is 3.80 with a standard deviation of 0.23, resulting in a verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree." The data suggest that the first indicative statement, "The displayed automobile encourages customers to take photos and share their experience on social media," received the highest mean score of 3.89 with a standard deviation of 0.33, interpreted as "Strongly Agree." Meanwhile, the third indicative statement, "The automobile display adds value to the overall dining experience at the café," received the lowest mean score of 3.71 with a standard deviation of 0.54 and was interpreted as "Strongly Agree."

Regarding the café environment, it shows that the respondents "Strongly Agree" on the café environment related to Prestige Automobile Design, with a composite mean of 3.76 and a standard deviation of 0.46. Item 5 of the indicative statement "The automobile display contributes to a unique and memorable café experience" had the highest mean of 3.83 and had the lowest standard deviation of 0.40 from the respondents. On the other hand, item 2 of the indicative statement "The prestige automobile display influences my

choice of seating within the café area" received the lowest mean of 3.68 and had the highest standard deviation of 0.57.

Regarding visual Appeal, it shows that the prestige automobile display in terms of visual Appeal got the verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree" with a composite mean of 3.82 and a standard deviation of 0.42. "The automobile's design details are visually impressive and draw attention" of the indicative statement got the highest mean of 3.85 and a standard deviation of 0.38. On the opposite side, "The prestige automobile's design details are visually impressive and draw attention" got the lowest mean of 3.80 and standard deviation of 0.44, and "The presence of a high-end automobile display makes the restaurant's interior design feel more elegant" got the same mean score of 3.80 and highest standard deviation of 0.45. The prestige automobile display results summary indicates the overall computed mean of 3.79 and a standard deviation of 0.44, which is interpreted as "Strongly Agree." As seen in the table, all indicators are "Strongly Agree." Visual Appeal has the highest mean for the indicators, with 3.82 for the mean and 0.44 for the standard deviation. The Café Environment got the lowest mean of all indicators, with a mean of 3.76 and a standard deviation of 0.46.

The dining experience in terms of dining satisfaction revealed a composite mean of 3.73 and a standard deviation of 0.51 with a verbal interpretation of "Strongly Agree" for the dining experience in terms of dining satisfaction. Indicative statement number 1, "The restaurant's ambiance contributes to my overall dining satisfaction," got the highest mean of 3.80 and a standard deviation of 0.43. Meanwhile, the indicative number 4, "The menu variety provides ample choices to suit my preferences," got a mean of 3.64 and a standard deviation of 0.58.

The dining experience in terms of time spent shows that the respondents "Strongly Agree" on the dining experience in terms of time spent with a composite mean of 3.66 and a standard deviation of 0.56. Among the indicative statements, "Spending adequate time dining allows for better conversation and social interaction" got the highest mean of 3.74 and lowest standard deviation of 0.47. On the other hand, the indicative statement "I consider the duration of my meal to be more enjoyable when surrounded by a prestige automobile display" got the lowest mean of 3.56 and highest standard deviation of 0.62.

The dining experience regarding value for money shows that the respondents "Strongly Agree" with the dining experience regarding value for money with a composite mean of 3.61 and a standard deviation of 0.58. Among the indicative statements, "The prices at this upscale café are reasonable given the level of service provided" got the highest mean of 3.63 and lowest standard deviation of 0.56. On the other hand, the indicative statement "The quality of the dining experience justifies the prices at this café" got the lowest mean of 3.57 and standard deviation of 0.55.

The summary of dining experience of the mean and standard deviation of dining experience, with the composite mean of 3.67 and standard deviation of 0.55, is interpreted as "Strongly Agree." Dining satisfaction has the highest mean for the indicators, with 3.73 for the mean and 0.51 for the standard deviation. The value for money got the lowest mean in all indicators, with a mean of 3.61 and a standard deviation of 0.51.

RECOMMENDATION

The following recommendations were made based on the summary findings and conclusions given:

1. Given the positive reception of the automobile display, the café could explore ways to make the cars even more interactive.
2. Since respondents indicated that spending adequate time dining facilitates better social interaction, the café could consider optimizing seating arrangements to encourage group dining or more interactive spaces.
3. While the café's menu variety was positively rated, expanding or rotating the menu offerings may be beneficial to cater to a broader range of tastes and dietary preferences.
4. Although the automobile display contributes positively to the overall dining experience, its impact on customers' perceptions of value for money was less significant.
5. Since the automobile display is a key element of the café's Appeal, regularly rotating or updating the cars on display would help maintain customer interest and provide fresh experiences for returning patrons.
6. Create a dynamic café environment by adjusting lighting, music, and themes to suit different times of the day.
7. To reinforce the idea of value for money, Karrera could offer themed dining nights, such as pairing high-end meals with automotive-themed decorations.

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